

Multithreaded XIOS version adapted to many-core architectures, and supporting GRIB2 format
Deliverable D2.4

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Lead authors:

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique-Institut Pierre Simon Laplace (CNRS-IPSL): Yushan Wang, Yann Meurdesoif

Other contributing authors:

Centre Européen de Recherche et de Formation Avancée en Calcul Scientifique (CERFACS): Sophie Valcke

Contacts: esiwace@dkrz.de

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

The developments realised in XIOS to extend its parallel efficiency by adding multithreading capacity are presented. These will be available to users in the next release XIOS-3 planned for summer 2019.

The heavy workflow generated by the climate models and the hybrid architecture of modern computers require the XIOS library to extend its parallelism to the thread level. With this motivation, we developed a portable multithreaded interface for XIOS based on the concept of MPI endpoints. The multithreaded version of XIOS was developed and then integrated and tested in the LMDZ model. The performance report of the multithreaded XIOS is detailed in this deliverable. We also present in the appendix the detailed multithreaded interface.

2. Conclusion & Results

The different developments realised in the last 24 months greatly improve the parallel performance of the next official release of the XIOS.

The developed source code is currently available under subversion in the “dev/branch_openmp” of the XIOS repository and can be browsed at: http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/browser/XIOS/dev/branch_openmp

With the current multithreaded version of XIOS, we confirm a large improvement of performances compared to single-threaded XIOS. The multithreaded XIOS can reduce the time spent on IO in the client (i.e. model) part, thus reduce the whole execution time of the climate simulations. Preliminary results (section 4.3) show that an acceleration up to 3.4 can be reached on 8 threads for data output, depending of the used configuration, leading to a global acceleration of 1.18 on the whole climate simulation. What’s more interesting is that this gain in performance is obtained without using extra computing resources, but simply using more efficiently the resources already allocated for the model.

The MPI-endpoint approach used to implement the XIOS multithreaded version is portable, in the way that no extra MPI library or specific hardware is required, the developed MPI-EP lib is built on top of a standard MPI library. The same concept can be adapted to other MPI based models or libraries with simple modifications in the source code. Integrating the multithreaded XIOS into climate models is also simple since it follows the same concepts as the single-threaded XIOS version. In most case, it will lead to a code simplification since the gathering of data to the master thread is suppressed.

More tests and optimisations are already planned for the future to further increase the performance of the multithreaded XIOS.

We note here that the functionality of supporting GRIB2 format is not included in this deliverable but should be before end of October; justifications for this delay are provided below.

3. Project objectives

Given the key role that the XIOS library plays in the efficient execution of numerical simulations based on Earth System Models (ESMs), this deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of a

vast majority of the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	Yes
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	No
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	No

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	No
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	No
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

We describe here the developments and optimisations done in the XIOS library during the last 24 months. The most important improvements include the development of a multithreaded interface, which enables any MPI based parallel code to cope efficiently with OpenMP threads. The idea of such multithreaded interface comes from the MPI proposal brought up during the last MPI Forums and several papers [1][3] have already addressed the importance of MPI endpoints and have proposed the framework of MPI endpoints. We started the project by implementing the MPI endpoint interface in which OpenMP threads act in the same manner as MPI processes do. This interface adds a second level of parallelism without major modification to the target code: in our case the XIOS library. The resulting library is called the XIOS-endpoint, which keeps all the functionalities of the single threaded XIOS library, and can be easily branched to scientific models, for example the LMDZ model, with hybrid MPI/OpenMP parallelism. The XIOS-

endpoint library has been validated with multiple tests. Performance results and analysis are provided in this report.

We note here that the functionality of supporting GRIB2 format is not included in this deliverable. The delay is due to the critical loss of staff over 2017-2018 at ICHEC, in particular those familiar with C++, NetCDF and GRIB skills. Transform work (necessary for the change in row/column ordering differences between NetCDF and GRIB) was completed but is incompatible with changes in the current XIOS_DEV_CMIP6 branch and file coding in GRIB using the ecCodes library. New hires at ICHEC in Q2/Q3 2018 have alleviated pressure and will allow the completion of this work, but unfortunately not in time for the D2.4 deadline. The workplan and timetable regarding inclusion of GRIB2 format in XIOS is as follows:

- Integration of GRIB2 changes for grid definitions and test cases with the XIOS_DEV_CMIP6 branch - Sept 14, 2018
- Testing of GRIB2 transform development and update of test cases - Sept 28, 2018. The changes will be tested against existing tools for rectilinear, curvilinear and unstructured grids, comparing output against existing tools (CDO) using Python test scripts.
- Documentation on changes to the XIOS code and extension to GRIB definitions - Oct. 5, 2018.

4.1. Context of the project

The simulation models of climate systems, running on a large number of computing resources can produce a significant volume of data. At this scale, the I/O and the post-treatment of data becomes a bottleneck for the performance. For example, in the IPSL earth system model, a long simulation generates a lot of data. In the previous CMIP5 exercise, 167 numerical experiments were carried out to simulate the last millennium paleoclimate. Up to 2 PB of data and 5 million files were generated. In the CMIP6 exercise, we are expecting 14 PB of data. This result brings to us three main challenges: we need an efficient management of data and metadata definition; we need efficient production of data on the supercomputer; we also need to address the complexity and efficiency of a post-treatment chain to be suitable for distribution and analysis.

To answer these challenges, we refer to XIOS¹, a library dedicated to intense calculations that allows us to easily and efficiently manage the parallel I/O on the storage systems. XIOS uses the client/server scheme in which computing resources (server) are reserved exclusively for IO in order to minimise their impact on the performance of the climate models (client) (*c.f.* Figure 1). The clients, attached to the model processes, and servers are executed in parallel and communicate asynchronously. In this way, the I/O peaks can be smoothed out as data fluxes are constantly sent to the server throughout the simulation and the time spent on writing data on the server side can be overlapped completely by calculations on the client side (*c.f.* Figure & Figure 3).

¹ XIOS is developed by IPSL (Institut Pierre Simon Laplace) and Maison de la Simulation.

Figure 2 - Every component of IPSL earth model uses XIOS to manage the IO. Data is exchangeable between models through the OASIS coupler.

Figure 1 - XIOS uses a flexible data output descriptor through an external XML file. Asynchronous transfer between client and server provides better IO efficiency.

In addition to the client/server scheme, XIOS can also efficiently manage data transformations through the use of filters. Data can be transformed and sent to the output server, but it can also be sent back to the model for further calculations. Figure 4 shows the dataflow generated in XIOS. Each incoming data flux is assigned to a timestamp and each flux can be connected to one or more filters. Filters are connected to one or more input flux and generate new flux on output. All filters can be chained to achieve complex

treatment, and they are parallel and scalable. A more detailed presentation on XIOS can be found in the forge homepage².

Figure 3 – Without I/O servers. Computation alternates with system I/O. Without parallel I/O and no overlap between computation and I/O, it can lead to a significant increase of elapsed time.

Figure 3 – With I/O servers. I/O is parallel and can be overlapped with computation. IO peaks are smoothed, leading to constant charge of file system all along the simulation, without impact on computation time.

² <http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/wiki>

Figure 4 - XIOS generates an internal parallel workflow/dataflow.

XIOS is now well integrated in many climate simulation codes: LMDZ³, NEMO⁴, ORCHIDEE⁵, and DYNAMICO⁶. MétéoFrance and MetOffice also choose XIOS to manage the I/O for their models.

Although XIOS copes well with many models, there was one potential optimisation in XIOS which needed to be investigated at the beginning of ESIWACE: namely, to make XIOS multithreaded. The motivation of this optimisation includes 2 aspects. First of all, more and more work effort lies in data transformation. In climate simulations, we need to output many variables, on different grids and with temporal operations (sum, maximum, minimum, instant, etc.). Some data are computed based on arithmetic operations of other data (such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and exponentiation). All these “on-line post-treatments” are managed by the XIOS clients. Making the XIOS clients multithreaded means that they can then suit better the current hybrid architectures by taking advantages of all the available compute resources. Thus we can expect a significant gain of performance.

³ LMDZ is a general circulation model (or global climate model) developed since the 70s at the “Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique”, which includes several variants for the Earth and other planets (Mars, Titan, Venus, Exoplanets). The ‘Z’ in LMDZ stands for “zoom” (and the ‘LMD’ is for “Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique”). <http://lmdz.lmd.jussieu.fr>

⁴ Nucleus for European Modeling of the Ocean alias NEMO is a state-of-the-art modelling framework of ocean related engines. <https://www.nemo-ocean.eu>

⁵ ORCHIDEE is the land surface model of the IPSL (Institut Pierre Simon Laplace) Earth System Model. <https://orchidee.ipsl.fr>

⁶ The DYNAMICO project develops a new dynamical core for LMD-Z, the atmospheric general circulation model (GCM) part of IPSL-CM Earth System Model. <http://www.lmd.polytechnique.fr/~dubos/DYNAMICO/>

Figure 6 – Domain distribution in LMDZ.

Figure 5(a) – XIOS original configuration: only master thread can call an MPI routine.

Figure 7(b) - All threads participate in MPI calls.

The second motivation for making XIOS multithreaded comes from the parallel OpenMP implementation of some climate models. We take the LMDZ model as example to explain the need for multithreading in XIOS. Figure 7 gives an illustration of how the computational domain is decomposed and distributed inside the model. In the LMDZ model, the global domain is divided into sub-domains and each sub-domain is associated to one MPI process. Inside each sub-domain, OpenMP threads are used to accelerate the calculations. We can see in the figure that each OpenMP thread has its own data distribution. When plugged into XIOS, each sub-domain (or each MPI process) is treated by one XIOS client. The data exchange between client and XIOS servers is handled by MPI communications. Under the original configuration of LMDZ and XIOS, in order to write an output field, the master thread must gather the data from all threads, enters the workflow and calls XIOS routines (c.f. Figure 5(a)). There are two disadvantages about this method: first, we have to spend time on gathering information on the master thread. This does not only increase the memory use, but also implies an OpenMP barrier. Second, while the master thread enters the XIOS workflow, other threads are in the idle state while waiting for the master thread to distribute to each

thread the returned data of the workflow, which also leads to a waste of computing resources. With the multithreaded XIOS, all threads can call directly the XIOS workflow simultaneously and we avoid these two disadvantages (*c.f.* Figure 5(b)).

4.2. Development of multithreaded XIOS

There are two possible ways to make XIOS multithreaded. First of all, change the structure of XIOS. This method demands a lot of modification in the XIOS library and adds to the code complexity. Knowing that XIOS is about 100 000 lines of code, this method would be very time consuming. Each function of XIOS would have to be modified to be able to use OpenMP threads. Besides, the modification would not be portable. Every new functionality would require a new implementation for the OpenMP parallelism.

The second choice is to make the threads act as if they were MPI processes. As in the LMDZ model, each thread has in its possession one part of the domain distribution. If threads can call XIOS functions without gathering information on the master thread, we can benefit from the fact that memory transfer is no longer needed, and the workload per thread is less. The problem is that XIOS functions are based on the MPI library. The current MPI implementation does not differentiate between threads of one given process. Thus, calling MPI functions simultaneously by threads can lead to errors or crashes. The solution to this issue is to have a wrapper to the MPI interface for which threads act in a similar way as classical MPI processes. The idea is that before calling MPI routines inside XIOS, the threads will first pass through the wrapper, in which the communication information and the identity of the threads will be analysed. Some extra information can be added artificially to the MPI communication and threads can be differentiated. In this way, no conflict between threads can occur. This interface gives us the possibility to make XIOS multithreaded while only a small part of XIOS needs to be modified in the code level. Another important advantage of such an interface is that it is portable and can be adapted to other MPI based libraries.

4.2.1. Development of endpoint interface

In this project, we chose to implement the second method, i.e. an interface to handle the threads. To do so, we introduce the MPI endpoint, which is a concept proposed in the last MPI Forums. Several papers have already discussed the importance of such an idea and have introduced the framework of the MPI endpoint. Figure 8 shows the concept of the endpoint. In the MPI endpoint environment, each OpenMP thread will be associated with a unique rank (global endpoint rank), an endpoint communicator, and a local rank (rank inside the MPI process), which is very similar to the `OMP_THREAD_NUM` concept. The global endpoint rank will replace the role of the classic MPI rank and will be used in MPI communication calls.

Another important aspect about the MPI endpoint interface is that each endpoint has knowledge of the ranks of other endpoints in the same communicator. This knowledge is necessary because when executing an MPI communication, for example a point-to-point exchange, we need to know not only the ranks of sender/receiver threads, but also the thread number of the sender/receiver threads and the MPI ranks of the sender/receiver processes. This ranking information is implemented inside a map object included in the endpoint communicator class.

Figure 8 - Semantics of MPI endpoints.

In XIOS, we used the “probe” technique to search for arrived messages and then perform the receiving action. The principle is that the sender process executes the send operation as usual, however, to minimise the time spent on waiting for incoming messages, the receiver process first calls the MPI_Probe function to check if a message destined for it has been published. If yes, the process then executes the MPI_Recv function to receive the message. If not, the receiver process can carry on with other tasks or repeat the MPI_Probe and MPI_Recv actions if the required message is needed immediately. This technique works well in the original version of XIOS. However, if we introduce threads into this mechanism, problems can occur: the incoming message is labelled by the tag and receiver’s MPI rank. Because threads within a process share the MPI rank, and the message probed is always available in the message queue, it can lead to the problem of data race and thus the wrong thread can receive the message.

To solve this problem, we introduced the “matching-probe” technique. The idea of the method is that each thread is equipped with a local incoming message queue. Each time a thread calls an MPI function, for example MPI_Recv, it first calls the MPI_Mprobe function to query the MPI incoming message with any tag and from any source. Once a message is probed, the thread gets the handle to the incoming message and this specific message is erased from the MPI message queue. Then, the thread proceeds to the identification of the message to get the destination thread’s local rank and store the message handle in the local queue of the target thread. The thread repeats these steps until the MPI incoming message queue is empty. Then the thread performs the usual “probe” technique to query its local incoming message queue to check if the required message is available. If yes, it performs the MPI_Recv operation. With this “matching-probe” technique, we can assure that a message is probed only once and is received by the right receiver.

Figure 9 - How tag is defined in MPI endpoint interface.

Another issue needs to be clarified with this technique is how to identify the receiver's rank. The solution to this question is to use the tag argument. In the MPI environment, a tag is an integer ranging from 0 to 2^{31} depending on the implementation. We can explore the large range property of the tag to store in it information about the source and destination thread ranks. In our endpoint interface, we choose to limit the first 15 bits for the tag used in the classic MPI communication, the next 8 bits to store the sender thread's local rank, and the last 8 bits to store the receiver thread's local rank (*c.f.* Figure 9). In this way, with an extra analysis of the tag, we can identify the local ranks of the sender and the receiver in any P2P communication. As a result, when a thread probes a message, it knows exactly in which local queue the probed message should be stored. A tag contains the user-defined value for a certain communication. The MPI tag is computed in the endpoint interface with the help of the rank map and is used in the MPI calls.

Figure 10 shows the classic pattern of a P2P communication with the endpoint interface. Thread/endpoint rank 0 sends a message to thread/endpoint rank 3 with tag=1. The underlying MPI function called by the sender is indeed a send for MPI rank of 1 and tag=65537. From the receiver's point of view, the endpoint 3 is actually receiving a message from MPI rank 0 with tag=65537.

With the rank map, tag extension, and the matching-probe techniques, we are now able to call any P2P communication in the endpoint environment.

For collective communications, the situation is quite simple since only one thread of the process (generally the master thread) can make the MPI call. We apply a step-by-step execution pattern and no special technique is required. A step-by-step execution pattern consists of 3 steps (not necessarily in this order and not all steps are needed): arrangement of the source data, execution of the MPI function by all master/root threads, distribution or arrangement of the resulting data among threads.

For example, if we want to perform a broadcast operation, only 2 steps are needed (c.f. Figure). Firstly, the root thread along with the master threads of other processes perform the classic MPI_Bcast operation. Secondly, the root thread, and the master threads send data to other threads via local memory transfer.

Figure illustrates how the MPI_Allreduce function proceeds in the endpoint interface. First of all, we

Figure 10 - Illustration of a point-to-point communication in the MPI endpoint interface.

perform an intra-process "allreduce" operation: source data is reduced from slave threads to the master thread via local memory transfer. Next, all master threads call the classic MPI_Allreduce routine. Finally, all master threads send the updated reduced data to its slaves via local memory transfer.

Figure 11 - Illustration of MPI_Bcast.

Figure 12 - Illustration of MPI_Allreduce.

routines, such as `MPI_Wait`, `MPI_Intercomm_create` *etc.*, can be found in the technical report of the endpoint interface attached in the appendix of this deliverable.

We have also implemented some one-sided communication (remote memory access) functions in the endpoint interface. These functions allow threads to fetch data directly from the memory of other threads. Detailed information on this aspect can be found in the technical report.

4.2.2. Integration of endpoint interface (EP) to XIOS

The development of the endpoint interface for multithreaded XIOS library took about one and a half years. The main modifications to be carried out to integrate the endpoint interface to XIOS consisted of several aspects:

- The first requirement for using the endpoint interface is that the underlying MPI implementation must support the level-3 of thread support, which is `MPI_THREAD_MULTIPLE`. This means that if the MPI process is multi-threaded, multiple threads may each call MPI with no restrictions.
- The XIOS initialisation step is modified. In the new initialisation step, we invoke the endpoint environment. At this moment we create, from the global MPI communicator (for example `MPI_COMM_WORLD`), an endpoint communicator which acts as the new global communicator (`CXios::globalComm`).
- Because in the endpoint interface the threads are supposed to act like processes, threads allocated by different MPI processes can form a new communicator for which not all threads of the process will participate (for example, the splitting operation can lead to such cases, c.f. Figure 12 in appendix 4.5). We also redefined the OpenMP barrier so that the synchronisation can take place only for a certain number of threads inside of a MPI process, but not for all the threads allocated by the MPI process.
- Some parts of the XIOS code, which need to be executed sequentially are protected inside the OpenMP critical region. This involves the part of the code where XIOS clients open a file and read the metadata, or in the initialisation step where the clients need to parse the xml file.
- Another important aspect to be mentioned is that in XIOS, we have variables with static attribute. It means that the static variables are shared by all threads inside of the MPI process. Modification done to the static variable by one thread is a priori visible by other threads. In order to privatise the content of static variables for each thread, we define them as `threadprivate`. In this way, each thread will have its own copy of the variable and the modification of the variable remains local to each thread.
- One remark on the multithreaded XIOS is that only the clients are involved. The XIOS servers remain single threaded. The reason is that the XIOS servers are reliant on the NETCDF library in order to generate output files. This library, for the moment, does not support the use of OpenMP threads.

The main effort in the endpoint interface is that we redefined all MPI classes along with all the MPI routines that are used in the XIOS library. The current version of the interface includes about 7000 lines of code and is available on the forge server⁷. A technical report is also available in appendix 4.5, in which one can find more detail about how endpoint works and how the routines are implemented. We must note that the

⁷ http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/iomserver/browser/XIOS/dev/branch_openmp

thread-friendly XIOS library is still in the phase of optimisation. It will be released in the future with a XIOS stable version. All the functionalities of XIOS are preserved in this new multithreaded version. Of course, non-multithreaded models can still safely use the new XIOS version.

To use this multithreaded version of XIOS inside of a multithreaded model, some modifications are needed:

- The MPI multithreaded support level used in the model must be MPI_THREAD_MULTIPLE.
- The initialisation of XIOS must be called inside of a parallel region of the model.
- Data distribution of the global compute domain to threads must be done inside the model.
- Static variables, which are involved in XIOS calls, must be privatised by adding the threadprivate attribute.
- OpenMP master regions related to XIOS calls should be opened for all threads.

4.3. Performance of multithreaded XIOS with production configuration

In this section, we show some preliminary performance results of the multithreaded XIOS plugged in the LMDZ model. The runs have been performed on Curie supercomputer (TGCC, France) composed of 80640 Intel bi-socket Sandy Bridge cores (2x8 cores by node, at 2.7GHz).

4.3.1. Results with LMDZ workflow

The LMDZ workflow produces a daily output file containing up to 413 two-dimension variables and 187 three-dimension variables. According to the user’s need, the “output level” key argument can be changed in the xml file to select the desired variables to be written. In our tests, we choose to set “output_level=2” for a light output, and “output_level=11” for a full output. The LMDZ model has been modified according to the previous section. 18 files have been touched in total. We run the LMDZ code for one, two, and three-month simulations using 12 MPI client processes and 1 server process. Each client process has 8 OpenMP threads, which gives us 96 XIOS clients in total.

Output_level=2	1 month	2 month	3 month
Execution time with XIOS	1831 s	3602 s	5360 s
Execution time with XIOS-EP	1714 s	3331 s	4945 s
Gain in time	6.39%	7.52%	7.74%
Acceleration	1.07	1.08	1.08

Table 1 – Performance results of XIOS in LMDZ with light output.

$$\text{Gain in time} = (\text{execution time with XIOS} - \text{execution time with XIOS-EP}) / \text{execution time with XIOS}$$

$$\text{Acceleration} = \text{execution time with XIOS} / \text{execution time with XIOS-EP}$$

We see from Table 1 that, with light output (*i.e.* output data production of 1.1G/month), the use of multithreaded XIOS has slightly reduced the execution time of the LMDZ model. The reason why the acceleration is not significant lies in the fact that the workflow in this test case is not heavy enough for

XIOS. Most of the execution time is spent in the calculation in LMDZ. That's why we only observe a small acceleration.

Even though the acceleration in general is low, we still can observe that the longer the simulation lasts, the better the gain of execution time is (from 6.39% to 7.74%). The reason for this change in acceleration is that, even if XIOS-EP does reduce the time in the data processing and outputting, the initialisation of the endpoint environment takes longer than that of the XIOS without endpoint. Thus, the longer the simulation is, the better the initialisation extra time is covered by the IO reduced time.

Given these observations, we assume that we should obtain a better performance gain with XIOS-EP for heavier workflows and longer simulations.

In the next test, we change the output level to 11 (*i.e.* an output data production of 33G/month). This means that all the defined fields in the xml file will be written. This workflow is much heavier than that of the first test.

Table 2 gives the performance results of the LMDZ model with heavy output. The first observation from this table is that the gain in execution by using XIOS-EP is about 15%, which is better than that in the first test. This is coherent to our conclusion that the heavier the workflow is, the better the performance with XIOS-EP should be. The reason why we do not have a stable increase in the acceleration with respect to the simulation duration, is because the overhead of endpoint initialisation is already well covered by the heavy calculations of LMDZ in short simulations.

Output_level=11	1 month	2 month	3 month
Execution time with XIOS	2094 s	4093 s	6083 s
Execution time with XIOS-EP	1781 s	3456 s	5157 s
Gain in time	14.95%	15.56%	15.22%
Acceleration	1.18	1.18	1.18

Table 2 - Performance results of XIOS-EP in LMDZ with full output.

4.3.2. Result with CMIP6 workflow

In this test, we use the same workflow as in the CMIP6 exercise. This workflow generates one high frequency (every 3 hours) output file, one daily output file, one monthly output file, two restart output files, and 63 other output files (1.5GB/month, light workflow for PI control experiments). We used 24 XIOS client processes with 8 threads per process, corresponding to the number of LMDz processes and threads. The number of XIOS servers varies from 2 to 12. Table shows the results of this series of tests.

2 XIOS servers	1 month	2 month	3 month
Execution time with XIOS	944 s	1802 s	2688 s
Execution time with XIOS-EP	889 s	1608 s	2388 s
Gain in time	5.83%	10.77%	11.16%

Acceleration	1.06	1.12	1.13
4 XIOS servers	1 month	2 month	3 month
Execution time with XIOS	971 s	1798 s	2670 s
Execution time with XIOS-EP	899 s	1612 s	2371 s
Gain in time	7.42%	10.34%	11.20%
Acceleration	1.08	1.12	1.13

Table 3 - Performance results of XIOS in LMDZ with CMIP6 workflow.

Gain in time = (execution time with XIOS – execution time with XIOS-EP) / execution time with XIOS.

Acceleration = execution time with XIOS / execution time with XIOS-EP.

8 XIOS servers	1 month	2 month	3 month
Execution time with XIOS	976 s	1825 s	2709 s
Execution time with XIOS-EP	858 s	1626 s	2397 s
Gain in time	12.09%	10.90%	11.52%
Acceleration	1.14	1.12	1.13

12 XIOS servers	1 month	2 month	3 month
Execution time with XIOS	982 s	1847 s	2728 s
Execution time with XIOS-EP	880 s	1624 s	2408 s
Gain in time	10.39%	12.07%	11.73%
Acceleration	1.12	1.14	1.13

Table 3 Continued.

From the results shown in Table , we can say that the performance gain in general is about 11%, and this acceleration rate is stable across all the different test configurations. The number of XIOS servers does not change the performance acceleration, which means that the total execution time is still dominated by the calculation of the model.

In order to see clearly the benefit of XIOS-EP in the LMDZ model, we have to further breakdown the execution time to check the time spent in XIOS.

In the next run, we concentrate on measuring the time spent on the histwrite function of LMDZ. It is in this function the xios_send_field routine is invoked. With the single threaded XIOS library, threads in LMDZ gather data to the master thread, which calls the xios_send_field function while other threads wait (c.f. Figure 5(a)). With multithreaded XIOS, the gather step is skipped and all threads call the xios_send_field function simultaneously (c.f. Figure 5(b)). We rerun the LMDZ model with 24 client processes and 12 servers. The duration of simulation is set to 91 days and the number of threads per process is 8.

The execution report generated by LMDZ with single threaded XIOS shows that the total time spent on the model is 2728 seconds, in which 433 seconds were spent by the histwrite function. The same run with multithreaded XIOS took 2412 seconds, and 126 seconds were taken by hiswrite. We can therefore say from these results that the reduction in the execution time, roughly about 310 seconds, by using XIOS-EP is represented by the reduction in time spent in the histwrite function. If we look deeper into this function, we observe that the gain of 310 seconds consists of two parts. Firstly, the data gather step is omitted. This gather step took 140 seconds in the test with single threaded XIOS. The second part lies in the fact that all threads send their data to the server simultaneously. In the single-threaded XIOS case, the send operation takes $433-140=293$ seconds while in the multithreaded XIOS it takes 126 seconds. We can say that, with the multithreaded XIOS we obtain an acceleration of $433/126 \approx 3.4$ for the output.

	Execution time	histwrite time	Data gather time	XIOS send time
LMDZ with XIOS	2728 s	433 s	140 s	293 s
LMDZ with XIOS-EP	2412 s	126 s	-	126 s

Table 4 - Time breakdown of the test to evaluate the benefice of XIOS-EP.

In the next test, we change the number of threads (2, 4, 6, 8) to observe the impact of using XIOS-EP in the LMDZ model.

		Execution time	histwrite time	Data gather time	XIOS send time	Acceleration for outputs (histwrite)
2 threads per proc	XIOS	2849 s	165 s	60 s	105 s	2.29
	XIOS-EP	2749 s	72 s	-	72 s	
4 threads per proc	XIOS	1547 s	152 s	50 s	102 s	2.98
	XIOS-EP	1439 s	51 s	-	51 s	
6 threads per proc	XIOS	1176 s	166 s	61 s	105 s	3.53
	XIOS-EP	1030 s	47 s	-	47 s	
8 threads per proc	XIOS	951 s	148 s	48 s	100 s	3.36
	XIOS-EP	836 s	44 s	-	44 s	

Table 5 - Performance results of LMDZ and XIOS using different number of OpenMP threads. (31 days simulation)

$$\text{Acceleration} = \text{"histwrite" time with XIOS} / \text{"histwrite" time with XIOS-EP}$$

From Table 5, we can compute the acceleration of IO obtained by using XIOS-EP. With the increasing number of OpenMP threads per process, the acceleration of IO is increasing from 2.29 to 3.53. The acceleration of the execution time for the LMDZ simulation is also increasing with respect to the number of threads: $2849/2749 \approx 1.04$, $1547/1439 \approx 1.07$, $1176/1030 \approx 1.14$, and $951/836 \approx 1.14$ for 2, 4, 6, and 8 threads respectively. The more threads we use, the better the performance of XIOS-EP compared to XIOS is. We can also observe from the table that the XIOS send time is stable when using XIOS. This is because the amount of data gathered on the master thread is constant no matter how many threads per process we use. Thus the time is not changing. On contrary, when XIOS-EP is used, the XIOS send time decreases with respect to the increasing number of threads. This is due to the fact that the amount of data sent by each thread is decreasing.

4.4. Conclusion and perspectives

From the performance results shown in the previous section, we can say that XIOS-EP does reduce the time spent in LMDZ model by 10-16% depending on the workflow density. From Table 4, we can draw the conclusion that the percentage of IO in the whole LMDZ model is reduced from **16%** ($\approx 433/2728$) to **5%** ($\approx 126/2412$). One important remark on this improvement of performance is that it is completely free of charge: no extra computing resource is added. This is the essential advantage of the XIOS-EP library.

We have to point out that these performance results are very preliminary. In the next phase, we will concentrate on the optimisation of the XIOS-EP library. One possible optimisation lies in the distribution of data in LMDZ. This distribution is not well balanced between threads: threads, which include the north and south poles, have a heavier data charge comparing to other threads. In the future, we will work on a more balanced data distribution in LMDZ to further improve the performance. We also plan to test XIOS-EP with more process in order to check the scalability of the library.

4.5. Appendix – Technical report on the development of endpoint interface

4.5.1. Endpoint semantics

The principle of MPI endpoint is to use threads as if they are MPI processes. Each thread will be assigned a rank and be associated with an endpoints communicator. We respect the convention that one OpenMP thread corresponds to one endpoint (*c.f.* Figure 8).

Endpoints are created from the following function:

```
int MPI_Comm_create_endpoints(MPI_Comm parent_comm,
                             int num_ep,
                             MPI_Info info,
                             MPI_Comm out_comm_hdls[])
```

In this function called by the master threads, `parent_comm` is the classic MPI communicator from which we create endpoints. Integer `num_ep` is the number of endpoints we want to create for the process. This argument can have a different value across processes. `info` is an output argument in which we can store some information about the endpoints. The created endpoint communicator is stored in `out_comm_hdls`, which is an array of endpoint communicators. Once the call ends, each thread can then fetch its own endpoint communicator from this array according to the thread ID or in some user-defined order. "After it has been created, the output endpoint communicator behaves as a normal communicator. The MPI calls on each endpoint (*i.e.* communicator handle) behave as though they originated from a separate MPI process."^[1]

"Once created, endpoints behave as MPI processes. For example, all ranks in an endpoints communicator must participate in collective operations. A consequence of this semantic is that endpoints also have MPI process progress requirements; that operations on that endpoint are required to make progress only when an MPI operation (*e.g.* `MPI_Test`) is performed on that endpoint. This semantic enables an MPI implementation to logically separate endpoints, treat them independently within the progress engine, and eliminate synchronization in updating their state."^[3]

4.5.2. Implementation of endpoint types

In order to use endpoints, extra information is required to be associated to the current MPI data types. In this section, we show how the endpoint data types are defined on top of the classic MPI implementation.

MPI_Comm

In the endpoint interface, the MPI_Comm data type is composed by:

- bool is_ep;
 - is_ep = true => the communicator is an endpoint;
 - is_ep = false => the communicator is a normal communicator;
- bool is_intercomm;
 - is_intercomm = true => the endpoint communicator is an inter-communicator;
 - is_intercomm = false => the endpoint communicator is an intra-communicator;
- void *mpi_comm: handle to the parent MPI communicator;
- OMPbarrier *ep_barrier: openMP barrier, used for in-process synchronisation and is different from omp barrier;
- std::pair<int,int> size_rank_info[3]: topology information of the endpoint communicator:
 - size_rank_info[0] = (rank of the endpoint communicator, size of the endpoint communicator);
 - size_rank_info[1] = (in-process rank of the endpoint communicator, total number of endpoints in the current process);
 - size_rank_info[2] = (rank of the parent communicator, size of the parent communicator);
- MPI_Comm *comm_list: pointer to the array of endpoint communicators created from the current process;
- std::list<MPI_message> *message_queue: list of in-coming messages for the endpoint;
- std::map<int, std::pair<int,int>> *rank_map: a map composed by an integer key and a pair of integers. The integer key represents the rank of an endpoint. The mapped type (pair of integers) gives the in-process rank of the endpoint and the rank of its parent MPI process:
$$\text{rank_map}\rightarrow\text{at}(\text{ep_rank})=(\text{ep_rank_local}, \text{mpi_rank})$$
- std::map<int, int> *inter_rank_map: if the endpoint communicator is an inter-communicator, this map gives the inter-rank (to be explained in the inter-communicator section) of the endpoint:
$$\text{inter_rank_map}\rightarrow\text{at}(\text{ep_rank})=\text{inter_rank}$$
- void **my_buffer: buffer used for in-process communication between endpoints (available types of the buffer: int, float, double, char, long, unsigned long, and long long int).

MPI_Request

The redefinition of MPI_Request is very important in the endpoint interface. In this data type, we store information of the non-blocking point-to-point communication. Because we use the matching-probe technique to query the in-coming message for endpoints, extra information is needed:

- void *mpi_request: handle to the underlying MPI request;
- int ep_datatype: data type used in the p2p communication;

- MPI_Comm comm: handle to the communicator;
- int ep_src: rank of the source endpoint;
- int ep_tag: tag of the communication.
- int type: type of the communication:
 - 1 => non-blocking send or non-blocking synchronous send;
 - 2 => non-blocking receive but the message has not yet been probed;
 - 3 => the message for the non-blocking receive communication has been probed, and the non-blocking matching-receive communication has been issued.

MPI Status

Similar to the MPI_Request data type, the MPI_Status data type in the endpoint interface has some new components:

- void *mpi_status: handle to the underlying MPI status;
- int ep_datatype: data type used in the communication;
- int ep_src: rank of the source endpoint;
- int ep_tag: tag of the communication.

MPI Message

MPI_Message in the endpoint interface includes:

- void *mpi_message: handle to the classic MPI message;
- int ep_src: rank of the source endpoint;
- int ep_tag: tag of the communication.

Other types, such as MPI_Info, MPI_Aint, and MPI_Fint are also redefined in the endpoint interface.

4.5.3. Implementation of Point-to-point communications

In an endpoint point-to-point communication, we use the tag argument to distinguish the source and destination threads. To be able to add extra information to tag, we require that the tag value be represented using 31 bits in the underlying MPI implementation (*c.f.* Figure 9).

The tag is user-defined and the internal tag used in the underlying MPI call is computed from tag, source rank, and destination rank. Because of this extension of tag, wild-cards such as MPI_ANY_SOURCE and MPI_ANY_TAG will not be usable directly. An extra step of tag analysis is needed which leads to the message dequeuing mechanism.

In the classic MPI environment, each process has an incoming message queue. In the endpoint interface, messages for all threads inside one MPI process are stored in this MPI queue. With the MPI 3 standard, we use the MPI_Improbe routine to inquire the message queue and relocate, in chronological order, all incoming messages in the local message queue of the corresponding thread/endpoint (*c.f.* Figure 11).

Figure 11 - Illustration of the dequeuing mechanism in MPI endpoint interface.

The following MPI norms are well respected in the endpoint interface.

Messages are non-overtaking Incoming messages' order is important! If one thread is receiving multiple messages from the same source with the same tag, the receive order should be the same order in which the messages are sent. That is to say, the n^{th} sent message should be the n^{th} received message.

Progress If a pair of matching sends and receives has been initiated on two processes, then at least one of these two operations will complete, independently of other actions in the system: the send operation will complete, unless the receive is satisfied by another message, and completes; the receive operation will complete, unless the message sent is consumed by another matching receive that was posted at the same destination process.

In the endpoint interface, when one MPI_Irecv is issued, we first dequeue the MPI incoming message queue and distribute all incoming messages to the local queues according to the destination identifier. Next, the non-blocking receive request is added at the end of the request pending list. Third, the pending list is checked and the message with matching source, tag, and communicator will be received.

Because of the importance of message order, some communication completion functions must be discussed here such as MPI_Test and MPI_Wait. "The functions MPI_Wait and MPI_Test are used to complete a non-blocking communication. The completion of a send operation indicates that the sender is now free to update the locations in the send buffer (the send operation itself leaves the content of the send buffer unchanged). It does not indicate that the message has been received; rather, it may have been buffered by the communication subsystem. However, if a synchronous mode send was used, the completion of the send operation indicates that a matching receive was initiated, and that the message will eventually be received by this matching receive. The completion of a receive operation indicates that the receive buffer contains the received message, the receiver is now free to access it, and that the status object is set. It does not indicate that the matching send operation has completed (but indicates, of course, that the send was initiated)."[2]

Example 1: MPI_Test(MPI_Request *request, int *flag, MPI_Status *status)

- a) If request->type == 1, communication to be tested is indeed issued from a non-blocking send. The completion status is returned by the classic MPI routine:

```
MPI_Test(&request->mpi_request, flag, &status->mpi_status)
```

- b) If request->type == 2, it means that a non-blocking receive is called but the corresponding message is not yet probed. The request is in the pending list thus not yet completed. All incoming messages are once again probed and all pending requests are checked chronologically. If after the second check, the matching message is found, MPI_Imrecv is then called and the type is set to 3. Otherwise, the type is still 2, and flag = false is returned.
- c) If request->type == 3, this indicates that the request is issued from a non-blocking receive call and the matching message is been matching-received. The status of the communication is related to the status of the MPI_Imrecv function which is returned by the MPI function:

```
MPI_Test(&request->mpi_request, flag, &status->mpi_status)
```

Example 2: MPI_Wait(MPI_Request *request, MPI_Status *status)

- a) If request->type == 1, the communication to be completed is indeed issued from a non-blocking send. Jump to step **d**);
- b) If request->type == 2, it means that a non-blocking receive is called but the corresponding message is not yet probed. The request is in the pending list thus not yet completed. We repeat the incoming message probing and the pending request checking until the matching message is found. MPI_Imrecv is then called and the request type is set to 3. Jump to step **d**);
- c) If request->type == 3, this indicates that the request is issued from a non-blocking receive call and the matching message is been received. Jump to step **d**);
- d) We force the completion by calling:

```
MPI_Wait(&request->mpi_request, &status->mpi_status)
```

4.5.4. Implementation of collective communications

All MPI classic collective communications are performed as the following pattern:

- Intra-process communication using OpenMP. (*e.g.* data collection from slave threads to master thread.)
- Inter-process communication using MPI collective calls on master threads.
- Intra-process communication using OpenMP. (*e.g.* data distribution from master thread to slave threads.)

Example 1: MPI_Bcast(buffer, count, datatype, root = 4, comm) with comm composed by 4 MPI processes and 3 threads per process. (c.f. Figure)

We can consider the communicator as {proc 0 (0,1,2), proc 1 (3,4,5), proc 2 (6,7,8), proc 3 (9,10,11)}.

The following two steps accomplish this collective communication:

- We call MPI_Bcast(buffer, count, datatype, mpi_root = 1, mpi_comm) with processes of endpoint rank 0, 4, 6, and 9.
- Processes of endpoint rank 0, 4, 6, and 9 send the buffer to its slaves.

Example 2: MPI_Allreduce(sendbuf, recvbuf, count, datatype, op, comm) with comm the same as in example 1. (c.f. Figure)

This collective communication is performed by the following three steps:

- We perform an intra-process "allreduce" operation: master threads collect data from its slaves and perform the reduce operation.
- Master threads call the classic MPI_Allreduce routine.
- All master threads send the updated reduced data to its slaves.

Other collective communications have the similar execution pattern.

4.5.5. Implementation of inter-communicator

In XIOS, the inter-communicator is a very important component. For example, every XIOS client's and server's communications are inter-communications. As a result, our endpoint interface must support inter-communications.

4.5.5.1. The splitting of intra-communicator

Before talking about the inter-communicator, we will start by splitting the intra-communicator. The C prototype of the splitting routine is:

```
int MPI_Comm_split(MPI_Comm comm,
                  int color,
                  int key,
                  MPI_Comm *newcomm)
```

"This function partitions the group associated with comm into disjoint sub-groups, one for each value of color. Each subgroup contains all processes of the same color. Within each subgroup, the processes are ranked in the order defined by the value of the argument key, with ties broken according to their rank in the old group. A new communicator is created for each subgroup and returned in newcomm. A process may supply the color value MPI_UNDEFINED, in which case newcomm returns MPI_COMM_NULL. This is a collective call, but each process is permitted to provide different values for color and key."[2]

By definition of this routine, in the endpoint environment, each thread participating in the split operation will have only one colour (MPI_UNDEFINED is also considered to be one colour). However, from the process's point of view, it can have multiple colours.

Figure 12 shows the result of the communicator splitting in the sense of endpoint. Here we used the endpoint rank as key to assign the new rank of the thread in the resulting split intra-communicator.

Figure 12 - Illustration of communicator splitting in MPI endpoint.

Due to the fact that one process can have multiple colours for its threads, the splitting operation is executed by the following 4 steps (c.f. Figure 13):

- Master threads collect all colours from its slaves and communicate with each other to determine the total number of colours across the communicator.
- For each colour, the master thread checks all its slave threads to obtain the number of threads having the same colour.
- If at least one of the slave threads holds the colour, then the master thread takes this colour. If not, the master thread takes colour MPI_UNDEFINED. All master threads call classic communicator splitting routine with key = MPI_rank.
- For master threads holding a defined colour, we execute the endpoint creation routine according to the number of slave threads holding the same colour. The resulting endpoint communicators are then assigned to the slave threads.

Figure 13 - Illustration of the 4 steps in the communicator splitting procedure.

4.5.5.2. The creation of inter-communicator

In XIOS, the inter-communicators are created by the routine `MPI_Intercomm_create`, which is used to bind two intra-communicators into an inter-communicator. The C prototype is:

```
int MPI_Intercomm_create(MPI_Comm local_comm,
                        int local_leader,
                        MPI_Comm peer_comm,
                        int remote_leader,
                        int tag,
                        MPI_Comm *newintercomm)
```

According to the MPI standard [2], an inter-communication is a point-to-point communication between processes in different groups. All inter-communicator constructors are blocking except for `MPI_COMM_IDUP` and require that the local and remote groups be disjoint.

As in endpoint interface, the threads are considered as processes, the non-overlapping condition should be extended to the thread level, which means that one thread cannot, at the same time, belong to the local group and the remote group. However, the local and remote groups can share the parent process of the thread. As the endpoint interface is built upon an existing MPI implementation, which follows the non-overlapping condition at the process level, we can encounter issues in such case.

Before digging into the possible problem that we can encounter, we investigate in the case where the non-overlapping condition is perfectly respected.

Figure 14 – MPI inter-communicator creation.

As shown in Figure 14, we have two intra-communicators A and B and they are totally disjoint both at the thread and process level. Each of the communicators has a local leader. We also assume that both leaders belong to a peer communicator and have rank 4 and 9 respectively.

To create the inter-communicator, all threads from the left intra-communicator call:

```
MPI_Intercomm_create(commA,
    local_leader = 2,
    peer_comm,
    remote_leader = 9,
    tag,
    inter_comm)
```

and for threads of the right intra-communicator, they call:

```
MPI_Intercomm_create(commB,
    local_leader = 3,
    peer_comm,
    remote_leader = 4,
    tag,
    inter_comm)
```

To perform the inter-communicator creation, we follow the 3 steps (*c.f.* Figure 15):

- Determine the leaders and ranks at the process level;
- Call underlying MPI routine `MPI_Intercomm_create`;

- Create endpoints from process and assigned to threads.

Figure 15 - Illustration of the 3 steps in the creation of an inter-communicator.

Now we can look at the cases where an overlap is presented at the process level. If we have overlapping processes in the creation of inter-communicator, we should add a priority check to assign the process to only one intra-communicator. Several possibilities (c.f. Figure 16):

1. Process is shared and contains no local leader => process belongs to group with higher rank in `peer_comm`;
2. Process is shared and contains one local leader => process belongs to group with the leader;
3. Process is shared and contains both local leaders: leader change is performed and the peer communicator is set to `MPI_COMM_WORLD` and we note "group A" the group with smaller peer rank and "group B" the group with higher peer rank.
 - a) If group A has at least two processes, the leader of group A is changed to the master thread of the process with smallest rank except the overlapping process. The overlapping process belongs to group B.
 - b) If group A has only one process, and group B has at least two processes, then the leader of group B is changed to the master thread of the process with smallest rank except the overlapping process. The overlapping process belongs to group A.
 - c) If both group A and group B have only one process, then a one-process intra-communicator is created.

4.5.5.3. The merge of inter-communicators

The MPI routine:

```
MPI_Intercomm_Merge(MPI_Comm intercomm,  
                    int high,  
                    MPI_Comm *newintracomm)
```

creates an intra-communicator by merging the local and remote groups of an inter-communicator. "All processes should provide the same high value within each of the two groups. If processes in one group provided the value high=false and processes in the other group provided the value high=true then the union orders the "low" group before the "high" group. If all processes provided the same high argument then the order of the union is arbitrary. This call is blocking and collective within the union of the two groups." [2]

This routine can be considered as the inverse of MPI_Intercomm_create. In the inter-communicator creation function, all 5 cases are eventually transformed into the case where no MPI process is shared by two groups. It is from this case that the merge function takes place (c.f. Figure 17).

- The classic MPI_Intercomm_merge is called and an MPI intra-communicator is created from the two disjoint groups and MPI processes are ordered by the high value of the local leader.
- Endpoints are created based on the MPI intra-communicator and the new endpoint ranks are ordered according to the high value of each thread and then to the original endpoint ranks in the inter-communicators.

4.5.6. Implementation of point-to-point communications on inter-communicator

In case of the inter-communicators, the MPI_Comm class has 3 members to determine the topology along with the original rank_map:

- RANK_MAP local_rank_map[size of commA]: composed of the endpoint rank in commA' or commB';
- RANK_MAP remote_rank_map[size of commB]: = local_rank_map of remote group;
- RANK_MAP intercomm_rank_map[size of commB']: = rank_map of remote group';
- RANK_MAP rank_map: rank map of commA' or commB'.

For example, in the following configuration as shown in Figure 18:

Figure 16 - Different configurations of inter-communicator creation.

Figure 17 – Steps of the inter-communicator merge function.

For all endpoints in `commA`,

`local_rank_map`

={{(rank in `commA'` or `commB'`, rank of leader in `MPI_Comm_world`)}}
 ={{(1,0), (0,1), (2,1), (4,1)}}

`remote_rank_map`

={{(remote endpoints' rank in `commA'` or `commB'`, rank of remote leader in `MPI_Comm_world`)}}
 ={{(0,0), (1,1), (3,1), (5,1)}}

For all endpoints in `commA'`,

`intercomm_rank_map`

={{(remote endpoints local rank in `commA'` or `commB'`, remote endpoints MPI rank in `commA'` or `commB'`)}}
 ={{(0,0), (1,0)}}

`rank_map`

={{(local rank in `commA'`, mpi rank in `commA'`)}}
 ={{(0,0), (1,0), (0,1), (1,1), (0,2), (1,2)}}

For all endpoints in `comm B`,

`local_rank_map`

={{(rank in `commA'` or `commB'`, rank of leader in `MPI_Comm_world`)}}
 ={{(0,0), (1,1), (3,1), (5,1)}}

`remote_rank_map`

=(remote endpoints' rank in commA' or commB', rank of remote leader in MPI_Comm_world)}

={(1,0), (0,1), (2,1), (4,1)}

For all endpoints in commB',

intercomm_rank_map

=(remote endpoints local rank in commA' or commB', remote endpoints MPI rank in commA' or commB')

={(0,0), (1,0), (0,1), (1,1), (0,2), (1,2)}

rank_map ={(local rank in commB', mpi rank in commB')}

={(0,0), (1,0)}

When calling a p2p communication on an inter-communicator, we should:

- Determine if the source and the destination endpoints are in a same group by checking the "labels";
 - src_label = local_rank_map->at(src).second
 - dest_label = remote_rank_map->at(dest).second
- If src_label == dest_label, then the communication is in fact a intra-communication. The new source rank and destination rank, as well as the local ranks, are deduced by:
 - src_rank = local_rank_map->at(src).first
 - dest_rank = remote_rank_map->at(dest).first
 - src_rank_local = rank_map->at(src_rank).first
 - dest_rank_local = rank_map->at(dest_rank).first
- If src_label != dest_label, then the inter-communication is required. The new ranks are obtained by:
 - src_rank = local_rank_map->at(src).first
 - dest_rank = remote_rank_map->at(dest).first
 - src_rank_local = intercomm_rank_map->at(src_rank).first
 - dest_rank_local = rank_map->at(dest_rank).first
- Call MPI P2P function to start the communication.
 - If intra-communication, mpi_comm = commA'_mpi or commB'_mpi;
 - If inter-communication, mpi_comm = inter_comm_mpi.
 - c.f. Figure 19.

Figure 19 - Example of a point-to-point communication on a inter-communicator.

4.5.7. Implementation of one-sided communications

The one-sided communication is a type of communication which involves only one process to specify all communication parameters, both for the sending side and the receiving side. To extend this type of communication in the context of endpoints, we encounter some limitations. In the current work, the one-sided communication can only be used in the client-server mode which means that RMA(remote memory access) can occur only between a server and a client.

The construction of RMA windows is illustrated in Figure 20:

- We determine the max number of threads N in the endpoint environment (N=3 in the example);
- On the server side, N windows are declared and associated with the same memory address;
- We start a loop : $i = 0, \dots, N-1$
 - Each endpoint with thread number i declares an RMA window;
 - The link between windows on the client side and the i^{th} window on the server side are created via MPI_Win_created;
 - If the number of threads on a certain process is less than N, then a NULL pointer is used as memory address.

Figure 20 - Illustration of the windows creation in the MPI endpoint interface.

With the RMA windows created, we can then perform some communications: `MPI_Put`, `MPI_Get`, `MPI_Accumulate`, `MPI_Get_accumulate`, `MPI_Fetch_and_op`, `MPI_Compare_and_swap`, etc.

The main idea of any of the mentioned communications is to identify the threads which are involved in the connection. For example, if we want to perform a put operation from endpoint 2 to the server, knowing that endpoint 2 is the thread 0 of process 1, the 0th window (win A) of the server side should be used. Once the sender and the receiver are identified, the `MPI_Put` communication can be established.

Other RMA functions, such as `MPI_Win_allocate`, `MPI_win_Fence`, and `MPI_Win_free`, remain nearly the same and we will skip the detail in this report.

5. References (Bibliography)

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6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

Publications in preparation OR submitted

Not applicable.

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience: The described implementations will be released in scope of XIOS3.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

We note here that the functionality of supporting GRIB2 format is not included in this deliverable. The delay is due to the critical loss of staff over 2017-2018 at ICHEC, in particular those familiar with C++, NetCDF and GRIB skills. Transform work (necessary for the change in row/column ordering differences between NetCDF and GRIB) was completed but is incompatible with changes in the current XIOS_DEV_CMIP6 branch and file coding in GRIB using the ecCodes library. New hires at ICHEC in Q2/Q3 2018 have alleviated pressure and will allow the completion of this work, but unfortunately not in time for the D2.4 deadline.

9. Sustainability

9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

The MPI-EP library developed for XIOS multithreaded version has the potential to be used for other codes based on MPI only to implement easily multithreaded (openMP) capability. For example it may be tested for NEMO or OASIS.

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable has no direct link with other deliverables. It will have synergy with ESIWACE 2 and the third phase of the infrastructure project IS-ENES 3. It will have synergy with all models using XIOS (IPSL ESM, CNRM-ESM, EC-Earth, UK-ESM and NEMO consortium).

10. Dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Location , dates	Audience	Zenodo record / link to website	Estimated number of persons reached
Training	XIOS tutorial	December 2015, Maison de la Simulation, Saclay (FR)	Scientific Community	http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/raw-attachment/wiki/WikiStart/XIOS-tutorial.pdf	30
Participation to a workshop	Yann Meurdesoif, IPSL XIOS: From "in Situ" post-treatment and interpolation of model data towards a new coupling functionalities Fourth Workshop on Coupling Technologies for Earth System Models	20-22 March 2017, Princeton (USA)	Scientific Community	https://www.earthsystemcog.org/projects/cw2017/program	70
Participation to a workshop	Yann Meurdesoif, IPSL Output whole CMIP6 data through the news XIOS parallel workflow functionalities 5th ENES HPC Workshop	17-18 May 2018, Lecce(IT)	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/5th-enes-hpc-workshop/presentations	50

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

None.